

Energy, Momentum and Running Time and Space X Variables?

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In Newtonian mechanics, time and space are measured by external clocks and rulers in an absolute sense. Special relativity changed this view of absolute time and space, but we argue there is a further issue linked to time and space and that is the idea of “running variables”. In particular, one may have a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$. The spatial variable, which is completely arbitrary, remains constant while time is a “running variable” or dynamic. This time may be measured by an external Newtonian clock, but if this clock is removed, does the concept of time disappear? We argue it does not and that mass (or energy) must keep internal time, i.e. somehow create periodic time intervals or an internal clock. The question is: Are these constant time intervals for all energy values? Is there a way to quantify these intervals? We wish to examine this here.

One may note that for the rest mass at $x=0$, time and x are treated differently. Time is a running variable and x is not. For x to be a running variable, a constant speed needs to appear together with a direction. If time as a running variable creates its own internal clock, we argue motion in one direction should create an internal ruler. Are the ruler gradations based on the magnitude of v alone? Interestingly, we note that for x to be a running variable, the magnitude of v is irrelevant. One simply needs a v with a direction. Furthermore, if external rulers and clocks are removed, there should be a physical attribute (which may be measured without them) which accounts for the internal ruler. We argue this attribute is momentum (mv nonrelativistically, $mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in special relativity). Momentum may be measured without using an external ruler and clock by noting the damage done upon collision with a target. Thus different m_0, v pairs lead to the same momentum value and the same internal ruler.

Is there a quantitative way to analyse the proposed internal clock and ruler? We argue there is and that it follows from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$.

Time as a Running Variable

Time seems to differ from space x in that it is always a running variable, while x is not. For example, consider a particle with rest mass at $x=0$ (a completely arbitrary point). x remains constant, but time does not. Both time and x , however, are arbitrary in that they may be shifted. Thus we argue that the idea of running variables is key i.e. there is a certain dynamical feature linked to space and time.

In Newtonian mechanics, one thinks of a fixed clock and ruler. These were originally considered to be absolute. Special relativity changed that notion showing that ruler gradations and clock periods differ in frames travelling at constant speeds to each other. This feature, however, is dependent strictly on the magnitude of velocity v .

Returning to the mass m_0 at $x=0$, one may ask: Does the notion of time disappear if the external clock is removed? We argue it does not. Time, however, is measured in a periodic way (intervals), so this seems to imply that a rest mass (equivalent to an energy) is associated with some kind of periodic behaviour in time which appears to be a non-Newtonian notion. How does one quantify this? We argued above that time represents arbitrary numbers, but if it is a “running

variable” it should be linked with a kind of “speed” or rate of change. We argue that this follows from a Lorentz invariant that is linear in t and linked to energy. This invariant is:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

For $p=0$, $A=-Et$ so that $dA/dt = -E$ ((2)). Energy is thus the rate associated with the running variable time in an internal clock. In other words, there is dynamical behaviour in time even without any motion in space.

Space X as a Running Variable

As noted, for a particle at rest, x is completely arbitrary and not a running variable while time is. How does one make x a running variable? The particle needs to move with a constant v in a certain direction. Energy, as a consequence, will change, but time is still a running variable, but with a different E and hence a different rate i.e. frequency proportional to $1/E$. Just as in the case of a rest mass with an external clock being removed, if an external ruler is removed is the sense of space eliminated for a particle moving at constant v ? We argue it is not.

The next question is whether the internal ruler created is only based on speed i.e. the magnitude of velocity? For instance, it is known from special relativity that a ruler “shrinks” in a constantly moving frame, as seen from a rest frame, and that this shrinking is based solely on the magnitude of v and c the speed of light in a vacuum. We argue this cannot be the case for an internal ruler, because speed depends on an external clock and ruler for its measurements. We argue that there must be an internal property which creates an internal ruler, but does not depend on an external clock or ruler for its measurement. We suggest that momentum is this quantity because it may be measured by the damage caused to a target. As a result, different m_0, v combinations lead to the same momentum and damage. These particles with different rest m_0 and different v have the same internal ruler even though their speeds are different. Momentum, however, may be linked to Newton’s external clock and ruler through $p=mv$ nonrelativistically and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ relativistically. Thus velocity measures a dynamical change dx/dt , but momentum measures a different type of dynamism i.e $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$.

The Concept of Periodicity

In order to have an internal clock or internal ruler, one requires intervals or gradations and this requires some kind of periodic representation in time and space. To find this periodicity quantitatively, we use $A = -Et + px$ i.e.

$$dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \rightarrow id/dt \exp(-iEt) = -E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \rightarrow -id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2b))$$

Thus we argue that the quantum mechanical behaviour of a free particle is associated with the creation of an internal clock and ruler. For example, the internal ruler gradations are based on momentum which may be measured without using an external clock and ruler.

The Concept of Probability

In the above section we are argued for the existence of an internal clock and ruler with gradations or intervals, but these must be physically marked. A moving particle does not “mark” space externally, thus its behaviour must somehow create gradations. We argue that this leads to the notion of a regular periodic probability function with zero probability at the endpoints of a gradation unit. In other words, a particle with momentum p , moving through space, does not actually move smoothly, but is associated with different probabilities at different x values with a gradation unit (called a half wavelength). A collision at any of these x points, however, results in a full p impulse, but collisions do not have the same probability of occurring at each x within a half-wavelength. Physically this is manifested in 2-slit interference experiments etc.

Given that the particle has constant p , however, and that it moves through space and time, if an external clock and ruler are introduced, one should be able to find an average speed dx/dt . This speed should be measurable within dx lengths greater than a half-wavelength. Thus there is the appearance of a constant speed.

$\exp(ipx)$ from ((2b)) represents the two dimensional probability required to create internal ruler gradations. Why are two dimensions required? Even though p does not explicitly depend on a v value (i.e. different m_0, v pairs yield the same p), it must have a direction. The two dimensions of $\exp(ipx)$ describe the direction of motion because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are not identical. As noted, if one does bring in an external ruler and clock, there should be the semblance of constant motion in x i.e. each x point carries the same weight. Somehow $\exp(ipx)$ should map into this scenario and it does through $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ i.e. an AND probability result which removes motion. The result 1, however, carries no information about the speed v , which physically exists. Thus $W^*(x)W(x)$ = spatial density in quantum mechanics v “loses” physical information, we argue. It only explicitly carries information about the internal ruler gradations or their average in a bound case with a potential $V(x)$. The external clock and time result, however, may be obtained from the average kinetic energy which does require knowledge of the speed v i.e. an external ruler and clock (except in the case of $v=0$) i.e. the rest frame scenario.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in Newtonian mechanics one thinks in terms of an external clock and ruler and there is no issue with this. If this ruler or clock are removed, however, do the notions of time and space disappear? We argue they do not. What then creates the sense of say an internal clock for a particle with rest mass m_0 (energy) at $x=0$? For a particle at rest, there is no need for a sense of space because it is at a single point. The x number (e.g. $x=0$) assigned to this point is arbitrary. We argue that the sense of time must follow from the existence of energy and as a result there must be some kind of periodic feature in time associated with this energy because one has to count time as it is a running variable.

We argue that this periodicity may be quantified by using the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$. For $p=0$, $dA/dt = -Et$ and $id/dt \exp(-iEt) = -E \exp(-iEt)$. Thus $-E$ is like a rate of change in internal time

A rest particle has a running time, but no running x . To create a running x , one requires a constant speed in a certain direction. This speed may be measured by an external clock and

ruler, If these external measuring devices are removed, then the sense of space should still exist i.e there should be an internal ruler. The measurement of this internal ruler should not depend on the external clock or ruler (otherwise it is not internal). Momentum p may be measured by the damage it causes a target. Thus one does not need an external ruler or clock to measure it. Different m_0, v pairs may yield the same momentum value so speed is not the governing feature as it is in ruler contraction in special relativity. Again there should be internal periodicity in space so: $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. The two dimensions of this probability are used to indicate direction in space. We note that in both cases of internal time and space, there must be physical behaviour marking the start and endpoints of an interval (gradation). These are created by having 0 probability associated with the endpoints. Thus one has the $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$ behaviour of quantum mechanics.

A particle moving with a constant speed, which must be measured by an external ruler and clock, has a particular momentum related to its rest mass m_0 . $\exp(ipx)$ which gives a different probability to each x point within a half-wavelength \hbar/p , must somehow map into this result. We argue this occurs through $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ which removes motion. All knowledge of m_0 and v also disappears. Thus we argue that $W^*(x)W(x)$, which is space density in quantum mechanics, represents incomplete information.